

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF LOCAL DECISION-MAKING FOR COLLABORATIVE ROBOTS USING EDGE COMPUTING

Vladyslav Yevsieiev ¹, Svitlana Maksymova ¹, Amer Abu-Jassar ², Jafar Ababneh ³

¹Department of Computer-Integrated Technologies, Automation and Robotics, Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics, Ukraine

²Department of Computer Science, College of Information Technology, Amman Arab University, Amman, Jordan

³Cyber Security department, Faculty of Information Technology, Zarqa University, Zarqa, Jordan

ABSTRACT

The article presents a mathematical model of local decision-making for collaborative robots using Edge Computing technologies. The proposed approach allows agents to effectively find optimal or approximately optimal routes in an environment with moderate density obstacles without centralized control. The simulation confirmed the system's ability to dynamically adapt and high resistance to changes in external conditions. The results of the study demonstrate the prospects for using local strategies to increase the autonomy, speed, and scalability of multi-robot systems. The conclusions obtained open up opportunities for further development of hybrid control algorithms, integration of machine learning methods, and application in real production and service environments.

Keywords: Collaborative Robots, Local Decision-Making, Edge Computing, Mathematical Modeling, Autonomous Systems, Multi-Robot Systems, Trajectory Planning, Route Optimization, Obstacle Avoidance.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of autonomous systems, Internet of Things (IoT) and edge computing technologies opens up new opportunities for organizing effective, flexible and reliable cooperation between mobile robots. In traditional approaches, centralized control of a fleet of robots often becomes a critical vulnerability due to delays in data processing, dependence on communication stability and scalability limitations. In dynamic or partially unknown environments, collaborative robots must have the ability to independently process information, make decisions quickly and coordinate their actions with neighbors without constant coordination with the center [1]-[16]. It is in this context that the Edge Computing concept allows data processing locally at the level of each device or their small groups, which minimizes delays, increases the speed of system response and ensures stability in the event of network connection failures. The relevance of the research is due to the need to develop mathematical models that allow formalizing local decision-making processes in collaborative robot networks, optimizing data exchange and increasing adaptability to changes in external conditions [17]-[30].

The purpose of this work is to create a mathematical model of local decision-making for collaborative robots using the principles of Edge Computing, which will allow formalizing mechanisms for analyzing sensory information, choosing optimal actions, and coordinating with neighboring agents under conditions of limited computing resources and minimal data exchange. Therefore, different methods and approaches can also be used here [31]-[51].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Urbaniak D., Damsgaard S. B., Zhang W., Rosell J., Suárez R., and Suppa M. proposed a distributed control system for collaborative robotic systems using 5G Edge Computing, which allows for low latency, high data exchange rate, and flexibility in system scaling [52]. These solutions make it possible to implement highly efficient network architectures for coordinating agent actions in real

time. However, from the point of view of studying local decision-making strategies, the results on optimizing data transmission and minimizing delays in environments with a large number of agents can be used.

In the study of Zuo Q., Tao D., Qi T., Xie J., Zhou Z., Tian Z., and Mingyu Y., an optimization model for the interaction of industrial robots via the Industrial Internet of Things using Edge Computing [53] was developed, which allows for increasing the efficiency of coordination and adaptation to changing environmental conditions. This solution can be integrated to increase the robustness of local decision-making algorithms, but is not fully adapted to the conditions of high dynamic environment due to the focus on industrial installations.

In the article Sharma M., Tomar A. and Hazra A. reviewed the fundamental concepts, applications and challenges of using Edge Computing for Industry 5.0 [54], which allows to better understand the potential and limitations of this technology for collaborative robots. The results obtained can be used to develop a strategy for placing computing resources at local levels, but specific decision-making models require further development.

In the study Wang Y., Yang C., Lan S., Zhu L. and Zhang Y. conducted a comprehensive review of the collaboration between computing on end devices, the cloud and the periphery for deep learning [55], which makes it possible to integrate distributed learning methods into the local decision-making system. However, the proposed approaches are mainly focused on processing large amounts of data, which limits their direct effectiveness for lightweight agents with limited resources.

Rahman M. M., Khatun F., Jahan I., Devnath R. and Bhuiyan M. A. A. analyzed the role and prospects of collaborative robots in the context of Industry 5.0 [56], which emphasizes the importance of flexible, adaptive and intelligent systems that operate locally. These findings confirm the feasibility of using local strategies to improve the efficiency of interaction in dynamic environments.

Ma L. described the application of social entertainment robots with sensory systems and Edge Computing for collaborative musical performances [57], which demonstrates the capabilities of local data processing to ensure synchronization and adaptive behavior in real time. These ideas can be useful for building more flexible coordination algorithms in multi-agent systems.

Moon J., Hong D., Kim J., Kim S., Woo S., Choi H. and Moon C. propose the use of Edge Computing together with local data map platforms to increase the autonomy of robots for autonomous driving [58], which allows them to quickly adapt to environmental changes. This approach can be used to improve local decision-making when robots move in complex and changing environments.

Finally, the publication Cobots A. analyzes the challenges of implementing Edge Intelligence in industrial collaborative IIoT systems [59], where the importance of developing local computing capabilities to ensure autonomy and rapid decision-making is noted. The obtained data confirm the promising research of local strategies and can be used for further development of models for autonomous multi-agent systems in production conditions.

A MATHEMATICAL MODEL DEVELOPMENT FOR LOCAL DECISION-MAKING FOR COLLABORATIVE ROBOTS

Edge Computing (EG) is a computing model in which data processing is performed directly on devices or network nodes close to the data source, rather than centrally in the cloud or on a server. In the context of autonomous cooperation between robots, Edge Computing allows each robot to make decisions independently based on locally processed information, minimizing communication delays, increasing response speed, and reducing dependence on centralized control systems. This is critically important for systems where it is necessary to ensure rapid coordination of actions in a dynamic environment. Using the integration of Edge Computing and the Internet of Things (IoT), it makes it possible to provide the ability to exchange data between all participants directly or through local nodes, forming a distributed communication system. Thanks to this, robots can transfer information about the environment to each other, coordinate their actions, and form joint strategies without the need for a single decision-making center.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

Thus, the combination of EG and IoT creates a basis for creating decentralized, sustainable, high-speed collaborative robot cooperation systems, where each agent has autonomy in decision-making, but remains connected with others to achieve a common goal. To develop a mathematical model of local decision-making for collaborative robots, we maintain the following parameters and describe their purpose, which are presented in Table 1.

The mathematical model being developed is based on three key components: local information evaluation; decision-making based on weighted criteria; coordination of actions through limited data exchange with neighboring agents.

Table 1: Description of parameters and their purpose

Parameter	Description	Purpose
$S_i(t)$	Local sensor state of the robot	Source of information for situation analysis
$N_i(t)$	Set of neighboring robots	To whom is minimal information transmitted/received?
$E_i(t)$	Integrated environmental assessment	Traffic safety and efficiency assessment
w_1, w_2, w_3	Weighting factors	Balance between achieving the goal, avoiding obstacles, and maintaining group behavior
$U_{target}, U_{obstacle}, U_{neighbor}$	Utility functions for target, obstacles, neighbors	Determine the desirability of a specific action
$a_R^*(t)$	Selected solution for movement	Next step optimization
$M_i(t)$	Short data package	Reducing latency and network load

Let us formalize the local environment evaluation. Let the robot R_i be located at the point (x_i, y_i) of the workspace, then $S_i(t)$ is the local sensory state of the robot at time t , i.e. a set of environmental indicators (obstacles, targets or other robots). $N_i(t)$ is the set of neighboring robots with which the robot R_i , can exchange data at a given time (t) . Then the local environment evaluation function can be represented as follows:

$$E_i(t) = f(S_i(t)), \quad (1)$$

$E_i(t)$ – integrated assessment of safety and prospects of movement in each direction;
 $f(\cdot)$ – sensor data aggregation function (weighted average of distances to obstacles and integer points).

The robot decides on the next action by maximizing the utility function by multi-criteria optimization:

$$u_i(a, t) = w_1 \cdot U_{target}(R, t) - w_2 \cdot U_{obstacle}(R, t) + w_3 \cdot U_{neighbor}(R, t), \quad (2)$$

$a \in A_i$ – a set of possible actions (movement in the direction: up, down, left, right, stay);
 $U_{target}(R, t)$ – goal approximation function (how close the action gets to the goal);
 $U_{obstacle}(R, t)$ – obstacle collision risk function (decreases when approaching an obstacle);
 $U_{neighbor}(R, t)$ – Neighbor coordination function (prioritizing actions that ensure a safe distance from other robots);

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

w_1, w_2, w_3 – weighting factors of the importance of criteria (selected experimentally or adaptively).

– target potential ($U_{target}(a, t)$) can be represented by the following mathematical model:

$$U_{target}(R, t) = -k_{target} \cdot \|\rho_R(t) - \rho_{goal}\|^2, \quad (3)$$

$U_{target}(a, t)$ – potential gravity function of the robot R at a point in time t to the target position;

$\rho_R(t)$ – current robot R position in time t in the form of a coordinate vector (x_i, y_i) ;

ρ_{goal} – coordinates of the target where the robot should move;

$\|\cdot\|$ – Euclidean norm (distance);

k_{target} – the coefficient of attraction to the target, which determines the force of attraction.

Model (3), ensures the desire of each robot to move towards the target point, minimizing the distance to it.

– potential for interference ($U_{obstacle}(a, t)$) can be represented by the following mathematical model:

$$U_{obstacle}(R, t) = \sum_{o \in O} k_{obstacle} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\|\rho_R(t) - \rho_o\|^2}{2\sigma_o^2}\right), \quad (4)$$

$U_{obstacle}(R, t)$ – potential robot R repulsion function from obstacles at a given time t ;

O – set of obstacles in the environment;

ρ_o – obstacle coordinates o ;

$k_{obstacle}$ – the coefficient of repulsion from obstacles, which determines the force of repulsion;

σ_o – parameter that specifies the radius of influence of the obstacle (scattering).

Model (4) describes "repulsion fields" around obstacles, forcing robots to avoid collisions.

– neighbor potential ($U_{neighbor}(R, t)$) can be represented by the following mathematical model:

$$U_{neighbor}(R, t) = \sum_{b \in N_R(t)} k_{neighbor} \cdot (\|\rho_R(t) - \rho_b(t)\| - d_{desired})^2, \quad (5)$$

$U_{neighbor}(R, t)$ – potential robot R coordination function with neighbors at the time t ;

$N_R(t)$ – a set of robot neighbors for a robot R in time t (determined by distance or communication channels);

$\rho_b(t)$ – current position of the neighboring robot b ;

$k_{neighbor}$ – coefficient that determines the strength of coordination between robots;

$d_{desired}$ – desired distance between robots to maintain formation.

Model (5) allows maintaining an optimal distance between robots: avoiding both excessive crowding and scattering. Based on models 2-5, the optimal decision is made as follows:

$$a_R^*(t) = \arg \max_{a \in A_R} u_R(a, t), \quad (6)$$

$a_R^*(t)$ – optimal action for the robot R at a point in time t , which he chooses from all possible actions to maximize his utility function $u_R(a, t)$. This solution is the best from the point of view of local vision and current assessment of the situation;

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY**VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6**

$a \in A_R$ – set of available actions for the robot R at the time t . These can be movement options (forward, backward, left, right, go around an obstacle), change of speed, direction, or other local solutions;

$u_R(a, t)$ – utility function for robot R when performing action a at time t . It takes into account various factors, for example: proximity to the target (positive), proximity to obstacles (negative), maintaining formation with other robots (positive or negative depending on the situation).

Expression (6) describes the process of autonomous selection of the best action by each robot based on locally available information processed in Edge Computing mode. It minimizes dependence on centralized control, accelerates the reaction of robots to environmental changes, and ensures flexibility and adaptability of the collaborative robot system during research or information gathering.

Local state updating and limited data exchange occur after decisions are made: the robot updates its position; Sends a mini-packet of information only to its nearest neighbors $R_i \in N_i(t)$ using short messages:

$$M_i(t) = (x_i(t), y_i(t), v_i(t)), \quad (7)$$

$x_i(t), y_i(t)$ – new robot coordinates;

$v_i(t)$ – current local motion vector.

Expression (7) provides updating of the local environment map without loading the general network.

DEVELOPMENT OF A MODELING PROGRAM TO STUDY THE MECHANISMS OF ANALYZING SENSORY INFORMATION, CHOOSING OPTIMAL ACTIONS, AND COORDINATING WITH NEIGHBORING AGENTS UNDER CONDITIONS OF LIMITED COMPUTING RESOURCES AND MINIMAL DATA EXCHANGE

The choice of the Python programming language for developing a program for modeling mechanisms for analyzing sensory information, selecting optimal actions, and coordinating between agents under resource-constrained conditions is justified due to its high prototyping performance, rich set of libraries, and ease of working with scientific computing [60]-[62]. Python provides easy integration with data processing libraries such as NumPy and Matplotlib, which allows you to quickly implement complex mathematical models and visualize research results. Thanks to its active support for IoT tools and Edge Computing solutions, Python is an ideal choice for developing autonomous systems that require local data processing without significant delays. The flexibility of the syntax allows you to effectively manage interaction between agents even in complex environments with a large number of dynamic changes. Python also supports the development of scalable systems, which is important for the further transition from simulations to real implementation in Edge and IoT architectures.

Let us describe the most interesting moments of the implementation of the modeling program for studying the mechanisms of sensory information analysis, selection of optimal actions and coordination with neighboring agents under conditions of limited computing resources and minimal data exchange:

```
# --- Environment parameters ---GRID_SIZE = 20
NUM_AGENTS = 5
NUM_STEPS = 50
SENSOR_RANGE = 3
```

This code snippet sets the basic parameters of the simulation environment, specifying the grid size, number of agents, number of simulation steps, and the range of each agent's sensors. The GRID_SIZE variable specifies the size of the square area in which the robots will move. The NUM_AGENTS parameter specifies the number of robots that will explore the environment simultaneously. NUM_STEPS specifies the number of iterations that the robots must take to reach

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

the goal while avoiding obstacles. `SENSOR_RANGE` specifies the range within which the robots can detect each other to avoid collisions and coordinate actions.

```
# --- Environment initialization ---
obstacles = [(5,5), (6,5), (7,5), (10,10), (11,11), (12,12)]
target = (18, 18)
```

This code fragment defines the initial configuration of the environment for simulating the movement of agents, setting the positions of fixed obstacles and the target point to which the robots strive. The list of obstacles contains the coordinates of the cells that represent the obstacles that must be avoided during movement. The variable `target` specifies the coordinates of the final goal, which serves as the main guide for choosing the movement of the agents. Thanks to these parameters, the environment becomes dynamic and facilitates the testing of obstacle avoidance mechanisms and strategic route planning under conditions of limited information. This allows you to simulate realistic conditions for testing local decision-making algorithms.

```
# --- Agent initialization function ---
agents = [np.array([np.random.randint(0, GRID_SIZE), np.random.randint(0, GRID_SIZE)])
for _ in range(NUM_AGENTS)]
```

This code snippet creates the initial positions of the agents in the environment by randomly generating coordinates within the size of the grid. A separate position vector is generated for each agent, which allows us to model the distributed initial location of the robots in space. This approach provides variability in the initial conditions for studying their further interaction and decision-making.

```
# --- Utility functions ---
def U_target(agent_pos):
    dist = np.linalg.norm(agent_pos - target)
    return 1 / (dist + 1e-5) # The closer to the goal, the greater the utility
```

```
def U_obstacle(agent_pos):
    for obs in obstacles:
        if np.linalg.norm(agent_pos - obs) < 1.0:
            return -100 # Large negative value for approaching an obstacle
    return 0
```

```
def U_neighbor(agent_idx, new_pos, agents):
    u = 0
    for j, other in enumerate(agents):
        if j != agent_idx and np.linalg.norm(new_pos - other) < SENSOR_RANGE:
            u -= 1 / (np.linalg.norm(new_pos - other) + 1e-5) # Уникаємо зіткнень
    return u
```

This code snippet describes three functions that determine the utility of different situations for an agent. The `U_target` function calculates utility based on the distance to the target, encouraging agents to move closer to it. The `U_obstacle` function returns a large negative value if the agent gets too close to an obstacle, which helps avoid collisions. The `U_neighbor` function penalizes agents for getting too close to other agents within the sensitivity zone, encouraging safe coordination between them.

```
# --- Possible actions (one-cell move) ---
actions = [np.array([0,1]), np.array([1,0]), np.array([0,-1]), np.array([-1,0]), np.array([0,0])]
```

This code snippet defines a set of possible actions that agents can perform during the simulation. Actions include moving one cell up, down, right, left, or staying put. This provides agents with simple local movements in the grid environment. This choice of movements allows agents to flexibly respond to their environment and coordinate their actions.

```
# --- Simulating agent movement ---
```

```

paths = [[] for _ in range(NUM_AGENTS)]

for step in range(NUM_STEPS):
    new_agents = []
    for i, agent in enumerate(agents):
        best_action = None
        best_utility = -np.inf

        for action in actions:
            new_pos = agent + action
            if 0 <= new_pos[0] < GRID_SIZE and 0 <= new_pos[1] < GRID_SIZE:
                u = (U_target(new_pos) + U_obstacle(new_pos) + U_neighbor(i, new_pos, agents))
                if u > best_utility:
                    best_utility = u
                    best_action = action

        agents[i] = agents[i] + best_action
        paths[i].append(agents[i].copy())

```

This code snippet implements the basic simulation loop, where each agent chooses the optimal action over a given number of steps. For each agent, the possible moves are iterated over, and the best move is selected based on the calculation of the total utility. The utility is determined by taking into account the approach to the goal, the avoidance of obstacles, and the interaction with other agents. The selected move is applied to the agent, and the new position is recorded in the path for further analysis. This approach models local decision-making in an environment with limited computing resources.

CONDUCTING SIMULATION EXPERIMENTS AND ANALYZING THE RESULTS OBTAINED

Based on the developed models and simulation program, it is proposed to conduct the following experiment "Investigating the effectiveness of local decision-making by agents in an environment with a medium density of obstacles".

The purpose of this experiment is to analyze the ability of collaborative agents to find optimal or approximately optimal routes to a given goal using local decision-making strategies in conditions where the environment contains obstacles of moderate density.

The main task of the experiment is to assess how effectively agents adapt their trajectories to existing obstacles, avoiding collisions, minimizing the length of the path and ensuring that the end point is reached without global centralized planning. During the experiment, agents start moving from different starting positions and make decisions solely on the basis of local information about the environment, reacting to obstacles in their field of view. The obstacles are located in such a way as to necessitate a change in trajectories and demonstrate the effectiveness of local adaptation.

Since the strategy is local, the expected results are some deviations from the optimal route, the presence of additional steps to avoid obstacles, and a possible increase in the time to reach the goal compared to the ideal direct path. However, it is expected that most agents will successfully reach the target point even in the presence of complex environmental constraints. It is also predicted that local coordination between agents will minimize conflicts and avoid congestion on routes, which will indicate the operability of the algorithm in real scenarios with decentralized control. In general, the experiment is designed to show that even without centralized control, agents are able to effectively perform movement tasks in a complex environment thanks to simple and local interaction rules. The obtained results of the experiment are presented in Figure 1.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

The graph (Fig. 1) shows the trajectories of several collaborative robots with local decision-making in an environment with obstacles. Each trajectory has its own color, corresponding to an individual robot or group of robots. Solid lines with markers show the path along which the robots moved towards the target point. The green asterisk indicates the target position that the robots must reach. Black squares represent static obstacles that block certain sections of the route, forcing the robots to change their trajectory in real time.

Figure 1: Trajectory graph of collaborative robots with local decision-making

The basic principle of the work is to use only local information for decision-making, without centralized control or complete knowledge of the map. Qualitative analysis of the graph indicates that all robots successfully avoided collisions with obstacles and with each other, although some of them were forced to make significant deviations from a straight line to the goal. This demonstrates the effectiveness of local decision-making strategies in a complex environment. Most trajectories are broken and contain a both horizontal and vertical movement, which indicates flexibility in adapting to obstacles. There is some clustering of routes: several robots chose similar areas to avoid obstacles, which indicates the effectiveness of local communication or response to the general structure of the environment.

Quantitative analysis shows that the most efficient robots traveled the path with a minimum number of changes in direction and quickly adapted to the presence of obstacles. Other robots, especially those moving in more congested areas, spent more steps on bypassing and had a longer route length. It is also seen that movement through the middle of an area with a high concentration of obstacles was accompanied by an increase in the number of maneuvers, while robots that stuck to the flanks of the map had more direct trajectories. The robots did not fall into "traps" and always found a way out to the goal, which indicates sufficient intelligence of local decision-making rules.

The logical conclusion is that the use of local strategies in collaborative robots is appropriate even in environments with medium-density obstacles. The system demonstrates good scalability and the absence of critical dependence on central control. In addition, the results show that local decision-making allows robots not only to avoid static obstacles, but also to effectively coordinate with each other in a common space without prior route marking. Thus, the experiment confirms the hypothesis of the effectiveness of local control for collective navigation tasks in real conditions.

CONCLUSION

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

In this paper, a mathematical model of local decision-making for collaborative robots using Edge Computing technologies was developed and investigated. The experimental analysis confirmed the ability of the system to provide effective navigation of agents in an environment with moderate obstacle density without the need for centralized control. The results obtained demonstrated that the use of local strategies allows robots not only to successfully avoid collisions with obstacles, but also to coordinate their actions to achieve a given goal, even with limited information about the global environment. Trajectory analysis showed that robots are able to find optimal or approximately optimal routes due to flexible adaptation to environmental changes and dynamic path construction in real time. Local decision-making based on data processing directly on the Edge device increases the speed of robot response and reduces the load on the network infrastructure, which is an important advantage for the deployment of large multi-robot systems. The model also demonstrates high scalability and potential for application in real production and service environments. The results of the study suggest the potential for further development of local strategies aimed at increasing the efficiency of interaction between agents in conditions of limited resources and complex spatial constraints.

Future research involves expanding mathematical models by integrating methods for predicting environmental behavior, self-learning of agents based on reinforcement, and developing hybrid strategies that combine local and global approaches to achieve even greater efficiency. Particular attention is planned to be paid to studying the impact of different densities and dynamics of obstacles on routing efficiency, as well as adapting models to work in unstable or hostile environments. Thus, the results of this work create a solid foundation for the further development of new-generation intelligent multi-tasking systems based on Edge Computing.

REFERENCES

1. Chala, O., & et al. (2025). Mathematical Model Based on Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL) and Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (POMDP) for Modeling Cargo Movement For A Mobile Robots Group. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 5(4), 480-489.
2. Maksymova, S., & et al. (2024). Comparative Analysis of methods for Predicting the Trajectory of Object Movement in a Collaborative Robot-Manipulator Working Area. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(10), 38-48.
3. Yevsieiev, V., & et al. (2025). Development of a program for processing 3d models of objects in a collaborative robot workspace using an HD camera. *ACUMEN: International journal of multidisciplinary research*, 2(1), 194-210.
4. Demska, N., & et al. (2025). Analysis of Methods, Models and Algorithms for a Collaborative Robots Group Decentralized Control. *ACUMEN: International journal of multidisciplinary research*, 2(2), 235-249.
5. Gurin, D., & et al. (2024). Using the Kalman Filter to Represent Probabilistic Models for Determining the Location of a Person in Collaborative Robot Working Area. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(8), 66-75.
6. Yevsieiev, V., & et al. (2025). Development of a program for processing 3d models of objects in a collaborative robot workspace using an HD camera. *ACUMEN: International journal of multidisciplinary research*, 2(1), 194-210.
7. Abu-Jassar, A., Al-Sukhni, H., Al-Sharo, Y., Maksymova, S., Yevsieiev, V., & Lyashenko, V. (2024). Building a Route for a Mobile Robot Based on the BRRT and A*(H-BRRT) Algorithms for the Effective Development of Technological Innovations. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, 72(11), 294-306.
8. Al-Sharo, Y. M., Abu-Jassar, A. T., Sotnik, S., & Lyashenko, V. (2021). Neural networks as a tool for pattern recognition of fasteners. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, 69(10), 151-160.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY**VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6**

9. Abu-Jassar, A. T., Al-Sharo, Y. M., Lyashenko, V., & Sotnik, S. (2021). Some Features of Classifiers Implementation for Object Recognition in Specialized Computer systems. *TEM Journal: Technology, Education, Management, Informatics*, 10(4), 1645-1654.
10. Sotnik, S., Mustafa, S. K., Ahmad, M. A., Lyashenko, V., & Zeleniy, O. (2020). Some features of route planning as the basis in a mobile robot. *International Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering Research*, 8(5), 2074-2079.
11. Baker, J. H., Laariedh, F., Ahmad, M. A., Lyashenko, V., Sotnik, S., & Mustafa, S. K. (2021). Some interesting features of semantic model in Robotic Science. *SSRG International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, 69(7), 38-44.
12. Lyashenko, V., Abu-Jassar, A. T., Yevsieiev, V., & Maksymova, S. (2023). Automated Monitoring and Visualization System in Production. *International Research Journal of Multidisciplinary Technovation*, 5(6), 9-18.
13. Ahmad, M. A., Sinelnikova, T., Lyashenko, V., & Mustafa, S. K. (2020). Features of the construction and control of the navigation system of a mobile robot. *International Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering Research*, 8(4), 1445-1449.
14. Lyashenko, V., Laariedh, F., Ayaz, A. M., & Sotnik, S. (2021). Recognition of Voice Commands Based on Neural Network. *TEM Journal: Technology, Education, Management, Informatics*, 10(2), 583-591.
15. Sotnik S., & et al.. (2022). Key Directions for Development of Modern Expert Systems. *International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS)*, 6(5), 4-10.
16. Abu-Jassar, A. T., Attar, H., Amer, A., Lyashenko, V., Yevsieiev, V., & Solyman, A. (2025). Development and Investigation of Vision System for a Small-Sized Mobile Humanoid Robot in a Smart Environment. *International Journal of Crowd Science*, 9(1), 29-43.
17. Nevliudov, I., & et al. (2025). A Small-Sized Robot Prototype Development Using 3D Printing. *acta mechanica et automatica*, 19(1).
18. Chala, O., & et al. (2024). Analysis of Systems for Coordination of Enterprise Subsystems Control. *Journal of universal science research*, 2(10), 127-137.
19. Yevsieiev, V., & et al. (2025). Development of a model for recognizing various objects and tools in a collaborative robot workspace. *ACUMEN: International journal of multidisciplinary research*, 2(1), 224-239.
20. Vzhesnievskyi, M., & Chala, O. (2024). Автоматизація внутрішньо-складських виробничих логістичних процесів для впровадження концепції Industry 4.0: енергоощадливість, продуктивність, мобільність, модульність, автономність. *Системи управління, навігації та зв'язку. Збірник наукових праць*, 2(76), 34-38.
21. Moiseev, M., & et al. (2024). Program Algorithm for Monitoring System Development. *Journal of universal science research*, 2(7), 33-43.
22. Abu-Jassar, A. T., Attar, H., Amer, A., Lyashenko, V., Yevsieiev, V., & Solyman, A. (2024). Remote Monitoring System of Patient Status in Social IoT Environments Using Amazon Web Services (AWS) Technologies and Smart Health Care. *International Journal of Crowd Science*, 8.
23. Hamdan, M., Kamal, I. W., Abu-Jassar, A., Maksymova, S., & Lyashenko, V. (2025). Prototyping of a two-wheeled mobile robot for sustainable manufacturing development based on triangulation method and software development. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 103(8), 3357-3370.
24. Tahseen A. J. A., & et al.. (2023). Binarization Methods in Multimedia Systems when Recognizing License Plates of Cars. *International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER)*, 7(2), 1-9.
25. Sotnik, S., & Lyashenko, V. (2022). Prospects for Introduction of Robotics in Service. *Prospects*, 6(5), 4-9.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY**VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6**

26. Babichev, A., & et al.. (2023). Wavelet Methodology for Analyzing Internet Marketing Metrics in Managing the Product Policy of the Business Entity. *International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research*, 7(5), 17-23.
27. Ahmad, M. A., Baker, J. H., Tvoroshenko, I., & Lyashenko, V. (2019). Computational complexity of the accessory function setting mechanism in fuzzy intellectual systems. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering*, 8(5), 2370-2377.
28. Lyashenko, V., Kobylin, O., & Ahmad, M. A. (2014). General methodology for implementation of image normalization procedure using its wavelet transform. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 3(11), 2870-2877.
29. Lyashenko, V. V., Babker, A. M. A. A., & Kobylin, O. A. (2016). The methodology of wavelet analysis as a tool for cytology preparations image processing. *Cukurova Medical Journal*, 41(3), 453-463.
30. Lyashenko, V. V., Matarneh, R., & Deineko, Z. V. (2016). Using the Properties of Wavelet Coefficients of Time Series for Image Analysis and Processing. *Journal of Computer Sciences and Applications*, 4(2), 27-34.
31. Ababneh, J., Abu-Jassar, A., Abuowaida, S., Liubchenko, V., & Lyashenko, V. (2024, December). Evaluation of Three Different Operators for Object Highlighting in Medical RGB Images: Canny, Roberts, and LoG in Independent Color Spaces. In *2024 25th International Arab Conference on Information Technology (ACIT)* (pp. 1-7). IEEE.
32. Orobinskyi, P., Deineko, Z., & Lyashenko, V. (2020). Comparative Characteristics of Filtration Methods in the Processing of Medical Images. *American Journal of Engineering Research*, 9(4), 20-25.
33. Mousavi, S. M. H., Lyashenko, V., & Prasath, V. B. S. (2019). Analysis of a robust edge detection system in different color spaces using color and depth images. *Computer Optics*, 43(4), 632-646.
34. Lyubchenko, V., Veretelnyk, K., Kots, P., & Lyashenko, V. (2024). Digital image segmentation procedure as an example of an NP-problem. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(4), 170-177.
35. Orobinskyi, P., Petrenko, D., & Lyashenko, V. (2019, February). Novel approach to computer-aided detection of lung nodules of difficult location with use of multifactorial models and deep neural networks. In *2019 IEEE 15th International Conference on the Experience of Designing and Application of CAD Systems (CADSM)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
36. Abu-Jassar, A., Al-Sharo, Y., Boboyorov, S., & Lyashenko, V. (2023, December). Contrast as a Method of Image Processing in Increasing Diagnostic Efficiency When Studying Liver Fatty Tissue Levels. In *2023 2nd International Engineering Conference on Electrical, Energy, and Artificial Intelligence (EICEEAI)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
37. Баранова В. В., Ляшенко В. В. Інфляція, вартість банківських ресурсів та мережа банківських філій – окремі аспекти впливу та взаємозалежності. *Економіка розвитку*. 2007. № 4. С. 64–67.
38. Sotnik, S. Overview: PHP and MySQL Features for Creating Modern Web Projects / S Sotnik, V. Manakov, V. Lyashenko // *International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IAISR)*. – 2023. – Vol. 7, Issue 1. – P. 11-17.
39. Lyashenko, V. V., Matarneh, R., Baranova, V., & Deineko, Z. V. (2016). Hurst Exponent as a Part of Wavelet Decomposition Coefficients to Measure Long-term Memory Time Series Based on Multiresolution Analysis. *American Journal of Systems and Software*, 4(2), 51-56.
40. Lyashenko, V. V., Matarneh, R., & Deineko, Z. V. (2016). Using the Properties of Wavelet Coefficients of Time Series for Image Analysis and Processing. *Journal of Computer Sciences and Applications*, 4(2), 27-34.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

41. Tvoroshenko, I., Lyashenko, V., Ayaz, A. M., Mustafa, S. K., & Alharbi, A. R. (2020). Modification of models intensive development ontologies by fuzzy logic. *International Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering Research*, 8(3), 939-944.
42. Matarneh, R., Tvoroshenko, I., & Lyashenko, V. (2019). Improving Fuzzy Network Models For the Analysis of Dynamic Interacting Processes in the State Space. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(4), 1687-1693.
43. Lyashenko, V., & et al.. (2016). The Methodology of Image Processing in the Study of the Properties of Fiber as a Reinforcing Agent in Polymer Compositions. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science*, 7(1), 15-18.
44. Kuzemin, A., Lyashenko, V., Bulavina, E., & Torojev, A. (2005). Analysis of movement of financial flows of economical agents as the basis for designing the system of economical security (general conception). In *Third international conference «Information research, applications, and education* (pp. 27-30).
45. Deineko, Zh., & et al.. (2021). Features of Database Types. *International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS)*, 5(10), 73-80.
46. Kobylin, O., & Lyashenko, V. (2020). Time Series Clustering Based on the K-Means Algorithm. *Journal La Multiapp*, 1(3), 1-7.
47. Vasiurenko, O., Baranova, V., & Lyashenko, V. (2024). Probability distributions of interest rates on loans and deposits in a study of banking activities. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(1), 49-56.
48. Omarov, M., Tykha, T., & Lyashenko, V. (2019). Use of Wavelet Techniques in the Study of Internet Marketing Metrics. *Eskişehir Technical University Journal of Science and Technology A-Applied Sciences and Engineering*, 20, 157-163.
49. Ahmad, M. A., Baker, J. H., Tvoroshenko, I., Kochura, L., & Lyashenko, V. (2020). Interactive Geoinformation Three-Dimensional Model of a Landscape Park Using Geoinformatics Tools. *International Journal on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology*, 10(5), 2005-2013.
50. Al-Sherrawi, M. H., Lyashenko, V., Edaan, E. M., & Sotnik, S. (2018). Corrosion as a source of destruction in construction. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 9(5), 306-314.
51. Lyashenko, V. V., Deineko, Z. V., & Ahmad, M. A. Properties of wavelet coefficients of self-similar time series. In *other words*, 9, 16.
52. Urbaniak, D., & et al. (2024). Distributed Control for Collaborative Robotic Systems Using 5G Edge Computing. *IEEE access*, 12, 148706-148718.
53. Zuo, Q., & et al. (2025). Industrial Internet Robot Collaboration System and Edge Computing Optimization. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.02492*.
54. Sharma, M., & et al. (2024). Edge computing for industry 5.0: Fundamental, applications and research challenges. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 11(11), 19070-19093.
55. Wang, Y., & et al. (2024). End-edge-cloud collaborative computing for deep learning: A comprehensive survey. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 26(4), 2647-2683.
56. Rahman, M. M., & et al. (2024). Cobotics: The Evolving Roles and Prospects of Next-Generation Collaborative Robots in Industry 5.0. *Journal of Robotics*, 2024(1), 2918089.
57. Ma, L. (2024). Application of social entertainment robot based on sensor and edge computing in collaborative music performance. *Entertainment Computing*, 51, 100741.
58. Moon, J., & et al. (2024). Enhancing autonomous driving robot systems with edge computing and LDM platforms. *Electronics*, 13(14), 2740.
59. Cobots, A. (2024). Challenges of Edge Intelligence-based IIoT 234 Collaborative robots (COBOTS) 201, 204, 205, 215, 216, 218–220, 251 compounded annual growth rate. *Artificial Intelligence*, 144(146), 148.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

60. Yevsieiev, V., & et al. (2024). A Program for Analyzing the Structure of a Web site Development Using the Parsing Method Based on the Python. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(4), 172-183.
61. Gurin, D., & et al. (2024). Web site reliability analysis using the python parsing method. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(5), 113-126.
62. Yevsieiev, V., & et al. (2024). Building a traffic route taking into account obstacles based on the A-star algorithm using the python language. *Technical Science Research In Uzbekistan*, 2(3), 103-112.

